

Chemically functionalized graphyne nanodots as an efficient adsorbent and sensitive detector of heavy metals: A first principles study

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Abstract

The potential of γ -graphyne for a wastewater treatment is scrutinized from the standpoint of its electronic, adsorption and optical properties with respect to heavy metal ions such as Hg^{+2} , Pb^{+2} , and Cd^{+2} using density functional theory calculations. The study includes the analysis of γ -graphyne nanodots before and after chemical modification with CN, COOH, SOH, NO_2 , and CH_3 groups. It is found that the molecular geometry of the investigated nanodots and their derivatives is planar. The stability and bond strengths of the molecules is examined using natural bond orbital analysis. Additionally, global parameters like dipole moment, chemical potential, electronegativity, chemical hardness, and binding energy are calculated. The CN, COOH, SOH, and NO_2 functional groups linked to γ -graphyne nanodots are favorable for intermolecular coordination with harmful transition metals, as shown by molecular electrostatic potential analysis. These functional groups decrease the band gap and increase reactivity of the γ -graphyne nanodots.

The computational absorption spectra of NO₂ functionalized γ -graphyne nanodots bound with Cd, Hg, and Pb are red-shifted compared to pristine nanodots, indicating that the functionalized nanodots can form strong complexes with heavy metals. Moreover, the intensity of absorption peaks allows one to clearly distinguish the species of bound heavy metal ions. This suggests that functionalized γ -graphyne nanodots are not only an effective adsorbent for heavy metals in wastewater treatment but also a sensitive detector that allows a non-invasive and remote optical read-out in a visible spectrum.

Keywords: graphyne nanodots; DFT; chemical functionalization; adsorption of heavy metals.

Introduction

Graphyne is a two dimensional carbon allotrope that combines sp- and sp²- hybridizations of carbon atoms in one structure[1]. It was theoretically predicted to exist in numerous modifications with varying sp- to sp²- atoms ratio $\eta = N_{sp}/N_{sp^2}$ [2] The three configurations that possess the same $p6m$ space group symmetry as graphene and are characterized by $\eta = 3, 2, 1$ are usually referred to as α -, β - and γ -graphynes, respectively. The three main graphyne structures were predicted to be stable and studied extensively [1,3–6]. However, γ -graphyne containing Clar's sextet [7,8] is the most stable configuration [2]. It can be viewed as an array of benzene rings connected via carbyne connectors. It has low thermal conductivity of about 8–76.4 W/(m K) [9–12], wide band gap of 2.3-2.58 eV [13,14], excellent intrinsic electron mobility comparable to that of graphene 1.62×10^4 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹[15,16], and mechanical properties characterized by Young's modulus 162.0 – 247.0 N/m [17–20] and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.38 \div 0.42.9$ [18,19,21,22]. Furthermore, γ -graphyne structure is equivalent to Kekule distorted hexagonal lattice and it exhibits nontrivial topological properties characterized by the bulk quadrupole moment [23,24]. Owing to this combination of properties, many practical applications such as gas separation [25–32], water desalinization[30,33–36], rechargeable batteries [37–39], hydrogen storage [40–44], and spintronics [45–

47] have been theoretically proposed and studied for γ -graphyne. Interaction of γ -graphynes with number of metals (V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, and Ni [45,48], La [49]) and gases (NO, NO₂, NH₃, CO, SO₂ and H₂S [50], O₂ [51], N₂ [52]) have been studied along with γ -graphyne properties being tuned with substitutional doping using Ge [53], N, B, Al [31,46,51,52,54], and O [55] as doping atoms. Recently several methods of producing γ -graphyne have been reported [13,14].

Quantum dots (QDs) are finite pieces of bulk materials wherein under the given conditions size quantization effect plays a significant role. Such structures were investigated for variety of two-dimensional materials: graphene [56–63], silicene [64,65], phosphorene [66–71], hexagonal boron nitride [72–81] etc. Some interesting properties have been predicted for the finite clusters of γ -graphynes too. The negative differential conductance [82], enhanced photovoltaic performance [83], topological corner states [23,24] are among them. Recently, the smallest γ -graphyne quantum dots have been produced in a form of a spoked wheel [84].

While providing many benefits, QDs are rather complicated structures that require careful systematic approach to their investigation. It is well known, for instance, that physical properties of the 2D material QDs can be drastically modified by their edges, shapes, sizes and surface functionalization [85–88]. The sensitive edges and large surface area are beneficial for enhanced adsorption properties that are useful for many of the above mentioned γ -graphynes applications including wastewater treatment, desalinization and etc. However, to the best of our knowledge such systematic studies of γ -graphyne QDs have not been reported yet. Here we theoretically investigate their potential for removal of heavy metals, namely Hg⁺², Pb⁺², and Cd⁺². Moreover, the effect of chemical functionalization on the electronic and the adsorption properties are considered.

2. Computational Methodology

The optimization of all investigated molecular structures in this study was carried out using the DFT/M06-2X/LANL2DZ approach [89–92]. TD-DFT was employed to compute the optical absorption spectra of γ -graphyne (Gp) and related materials at the M06-2X/LANL2DZ level, and all computations were performed using the Gaussian 16 software suite [89,90]. The natural bond orbital (NBO) analysis for γ -graphyne functionalized with NO₂ groups (Gp-NO₂) and its complex forms with heavy metals was conducted using the same level of theory in the gaseous state. It is noteworthy that the DFT/M06-2X/LANL2DZ level of theory demonstrated high accuracy in determining the optimal structures and electronic properties of Gp and its related materials [90,93–95].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Optimized molecular structures.

In Fig. 1, the optimum structures of the compounds graphyne (Gp) and its derivatives Gp-CH₃, Gp-COOH, Gp-CN, Gp-NO₂, and Gp-SOH are depicted. The Gp optimized structures were functionalized with the electron-withdrawing substituents COOH, CN, SOH, and NO₂ and the electron-donating substituent CH₃ to enhance their reactivity for the removal of toxic mercury (Hg⁺²), lead (Pb⁺²), and cadmium (Cd⁺²) from wastewater. All the investigated structures are planar, as shown in Fig. 1, with the phenyl groups in the same plane as the acetylenyl groups shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1. The following observations can be drawn from Fig. 1 and Table 1 regarding Gp and its based compounds: (1) The C9-C2-C1-C6 and C9-C2-C1-C6-dihedral angles are approximately 180.00° for Gp and its based materials. This is referred to as the planarity of every molecular arrangement under study. (2) The C1-C2-C3 and C1-C2-C3 bond angles for Gp and its compounds are

approximately 120.00° , indicating sp^2 hybridization of phenyl groups in all examined molecular structures.

Fig. 1 Optimized labeled molecular structures of Gp and its based materials using M06-2X/LANL2DZ level of theory in the gaseous phase.

(3) In addition, the C9-C15-C37 and C9-C15-C35 bond angles of Gp and the compounds derived from it are approximately 180.00°, indicating the sp hybridization of the acetylene group, which links the terminal phenyls with the central phenyl groups. (4) The electron-donor characteristics of the methyl group cause the C1-C2 and C3-C4 bond lengths of the Gp-CH₃ to be 0.001 Å shorter than those of the other molecular structures under study. (5) All of the systems under study (Gp, Gp-CH₃, Gp-COOH, Gp-CN, Gp-NO₂, and Gp-SOH) have flat side views. The optimized Gp and its variants' IR spectra are shown in Fig. S1, it can be seen that the absorption frequencies are positive (there are no imaginary frequencies), indicating that the obtained structures are geometrically stable.

Table 1. Some important quantum parameters like bond length (Å), dihedral, and bond angles (degrees) for Gp and its derivatives using the DFT/M06-2X/LANL2DZ method.

Designation	Gp	Designation	Gp-CH ₃	Gp-COOH	Gp-CN	Gp-NO ₂	Gp-SOH
C1-C2	1.416	C1-C2	1.415	1.416	1.416	1.416	1.416
C9-C15	1.219	C9-C15	1.218	1.219	1.218	1.219	1.218
C3-C4	1.416	C3-C4	1.415	1.416	1.416	1.416	1.416
C73-C74	1.219	C73-C74	1.220	1.218	1.218	1.217	1.218
C1-C2-C3	119.99	C1-C2-C3	120.00	119.99	120.00	119.99	119.96
C9-C15-C37	179.96	C9-C15-C35	179.97	179.99	179.98	179.98	179.74
C37-C38-C40	119.69	C37-C39-C40	121.36	120.10	120.13	118.65	118.74
C9-C2-C1-C6	179.99	C9-C2-C1-C6	179.99	179.99	180.00	179.99	179.92
C39-C37-C38-C75	179.99	C39-C37-C35-C15	179.83	179.99	180.00	179.99	179.82

3.2 HOMO/LUMO molecular orbitals

Notably, the explanation of the HOMO/LUMO molecular orbitals' energy gaps (E_g) is crucial for explaining the electronic properties of the systems under consideration [96]. HOMO energy (E_H) describes its electron-donating capability, while LUMO energy (E_L) describes the electron-withdrawing capability [96]. The

difference between E_H and E_L , represents the energy gap (E_g) [96]. Fig. 2 provides a graphical depiction of HOMO (H) and LUMO (L) for Gp before and after functionalization. As shown in Fig. 2, the center and terminal phenyls, as well as the acetylenyl bridge, are where the H and L MOs are localized in contrast to Gp and its derivatives. For Gp and its functionalized substances, the energy levels of H and L as well as the E_g values in the gaseous state are computed; the results are shown in Fig. 2. All structures under study have computed E_H and E_L values that fall between -6.502 and -8.192 eV and -1.864 and -3.773 eV, respectively. By comparing the value of E_H , Gp-NO₂ has the most stable HOMO and Gp-CH₃ has the least stable molecule structure. The most stable LUMO among compounds with comparable EL values are Gp-NO₂, whereas the least stable is Gp-CH₃ MGS. The E_g values are given in the following order for each of the molecular structures that were examined: Gp-NO₂< Gp-COOH< Gp-CN< Gp-SOH< Gp-CH₃< Gp. According to those findings, the Gp is the compound that is the most reliable when compared to the other MGSs. As a result, both functional groups that donate electrons and those that take them away make Gp more reactive. The most reactive molecular structure, according to the E_g values, is Gp-NO₂, because it has the greatest electron-withdrawing characteristics of the NO₂ functional group compared to Gp and other Gp-based substances. For Gp and its variants, the electronic density of states (DOS) is displayed in Fig. S2. The energy levels are obtained by Gaussian function $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\alpha}} \exp\left[-\frac{(\varepsilon-\varepsilon_i)^2}{2\alpha^2}\right]$ with broadening $\alpha = 0.1\text{eV}$. The Fermi level is fixed, $E_F = (E_{\text{HOMO}}+E_{\text{LUMO}})/2$. It is evident from Fig. S2 that the shape, functional group termination of the Gp, and chemical modification all have a significant impact on the energy levels. The energy gap of Gp is high (4.66 eV), whereas the energy gap of the Gp-NO₂ dot is smaller (4.41 eV). The functionalizing with either electron-

withdrawing (CN, NO₂, COOH, SOH) or electron-donating (CH₃) groups reduces the large energy gap in Gp.

Fig. 2 Graphical representation of HOMO/LUMO energies, molecular distribution, and energy gaps (E_g) for Gp with and without functionalization.

3.3 Quantum stability chemical (QSC) parameters

The dipole moment (μ), chemical potential (ρ), electronegativity (χ), chemical hardness (η), and binding energy (BE) per unit atom were determined using E_L and E_H values as part of assessing quantum stability chemical (QSC) parameters. These

QSC parameters are calculated by utilizing the subsequent equations $\rho = \frac{E_H + E_L}{2}$ [97], $\chi = -\frac{E_H + E_L}{2}$, $\eta = \frac{E_L - E_H}{2}$ and $BE = (N_X E_X + N_C E_C + N_H E_H - E_t)/N$. With N_X , N_C , N_H , and N_t are the number of X groups, X=CN, COOH, NO₂, SOH and CH₃, the number of carbon atoms, number of hydrogen atoms, and the total number of atoms, respectively. E_X , E_C , E_H , and E_t are the corresponding total energies of the functional groups, carbon atoms, hydrogen atoms, and the resultant compound, respectively.

It is worth noting that a structure with a high dipole moment (μ) exhibits significant asymmetry in its electronic charge distribution. According to Table 2, the Gp-COOH structure has the highest μ magnitude compared to the other structures, implying that intramolecular charge transfer in Gp-COOH is larger than in the other structures. Additionally, Table 2 shows that the Gp-NO₂ structure has a lower ρ value compared to the other systems, indicating that Gp-NO₂ donates electrons easier in contrast to the other molecular structures under study. Conversely, Gp-NO₂ has the highest χ value, indicating its superior ability to attract electrons compared to the other structures. The η value for Gp is noticeably higher compared to the other structures, indicating that Gp is more resistant to releasing electrons, whereas the other structures are more likely to donate electrons to another acceptor compound. The positive frequencies from the IR spectra, along with positive binding energy (BE) values, provide further confirmation of the stable formation of the considered functionalized systems. The Gp-NO₂ structure has the highest BE value, indicating that the NO₂ functional group attached to Gp has the highest stability compared to the other structures.

Table 2 Some important QSC parameters using the DFT/M06-2X/LANL2DZ method in the gaseous phase.

Nomenclature	L (eV)	H (eV)	E_g (eV)	ρ (eV)	χ (eV)	η (eV)	μ (D)	BE (eV)
Gp-CH ₃	-1.869	-6.502	4.63	-4.185	4.185	2.316	0.000041	17.027

Gp-COOH	-2.828	-7.324	4.49	-4.824	4.824	2.248	4.740199	96.645
Gp-NO ₂	-3.773	-8.192	4.41	-5.982	5.982	2.209	0.000245	111.634
Gp-CN	-3.280	-7.807	4.52	-5.736	5.736	2.263	0.000587	51.343
Gp-SOH	-2.918	-7.504	4.58	-5.211	5.211	2.293	7.270835	43.962
Gp	-2.071	-6.733	4.66	-4.402	4.402	2.331	0.001816	-

3.4 Molecular electrostatic potentials

The designed Gp and its derivatives' electrophilic versus nucleophilic sites are revealed by molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) research, which is useful for predicting reaction sites [98]. In Fig. 3, the MEPs are displayed. The MEP surface's color schematic is as follows: red for an electron-rich, partially negative charge; blue for an electron-deficient, partly positive charge; light blue for a region that is slightly electron-deficient; yellow for a region that is slightly electron-rich; and green for neutral (zero potential) (See Fig. 3). The acetylene bridge is surrounded by a negative region (red color), which suggests that electrophilic attacks are taking place there. The hydrogen and carbon atoms were all within the positive (blue) Gp zone, indicating that these sites are vulnerable to nucleophilic attack. The parts of the molecule that lack any charge distribution are known as the neutral regions (green in hue). Due to the high electron withdrawal that these groups exhibit, upon functionalizing Gp via (CN, COOH, SOH, and NO₂), the electrophilic attack (red color) regions are also on those groups as shown in Fig. 3. On the other hand, as shown in Fig. 3, the nucleophilic attack (blue color) of Gp-CH₃ is focused on the CH₃ group because of the strong electron-donating qualities of the CH₃ substituents. Additionally, owing to the methyl group's electron-donating properties, the CH₃ increases the electronic density on the acetylenic bridge. On the other hand, electron enrichment was linked to the red regions containing the CN, COOH, SOH, and NO₂ functional groups of Gp-CN, Gp-COOH, SOH, and Gp-NO₂ (i.e., electrophilic reactivity). Consequently, they become an ideal setting for intermolecular

coordination with dangerous transition metals like Hg^{+2} , Pb^{+2} , and Cd^{+2} that are found in contaminated water.

Fig. 3 Electrostatic potential map (ESP) for Gp and its based substances using M06-2X/LANL2DZ level of theory.

3.5 Gp-NO₂ complexes with heavy metals

In this study, the Gp-NO₂ ligand was chosen for its high binding energy to form complexes with heavy metal ions Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} . The ligand acts as a polydentate ligand, meaning it contains more than two atoms that donate electrons, such as O atoms. The complexes were optimized electronically using the DFT/M06-2X/LanL2DZ method in the gaseous state, and the results were shown in Fig. 4. The complexes of Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb were found to be planar,

with C-C-C-C-C dihedral angles at around 180.00°. The metal-ligand (M-L) bond distances for Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb were found to be within the ranges of 2.092→3.442Å. The M-L bond length for Gp-NO₂-Pb complexes was found to be shorter compared to Gp-NO₂-Cd and Gp-NO₂-Hg complexes, as shown in Fig. 4. This was due to the smaller size of Pb²⁺ compared to Hg²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions. All studied complexes had c-c-c bond angles within the range of 118→122°, indicating sp² hybridization. The symbol M refers to the heavy metal ions Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺, and Cd²⁺.

Gp-NO₂-Pb is the most stable structure among others due to its lower E_{ads} value and shorter bond lengths. The negative E_{ads} values confirmed the stability of Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb. In various studies, adsorption energy is used to differentiate between physical and chemical adsorption. [99]. Adsorption energy values between -0.3109 and -0.103643 eV fall under physical adsorption, while those between -9.949701 and -0.5182 eV indicate chemical adsorption [100]. In Fig. 4, the E_{ads} values for all harmful Gp-NO₂ metals range from -0.035 to -4.199 eV. Specifically, the computed E_{ads} values for Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb are -0.035, -0.090, and -4.199 eV, respectively. Thus, hazardous metal adsorption follows the order of Gp-NO₂-Pb < Gp-NO₂-Hg < Gp-NO₂-Cd due to the smaller size of Pb²⁺ compared to the other adsorbed heavy metals. Physisorption binds Cd²⁺ and Hg²⁺ to Gp-NO₂, while chemisorption-based adsorption binds Pb²⁺, resulting in a lower degree of reusability compared to the other adsorbed metals.

Fig. 4 The optimized structures of Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb complexes using the DFT/M06-2X/LANL2DZ method in a gaseous state. Additionally, adsorption energy (E_{ads}) were estimated.

3.6 HOMO/LUMO of complexes

In chemistry, the E_{HOMO} energy of a molecule refers to its ability to donate electrons, while the E_{LUMO} energy refers to its ability to withdraw electrons. The difference between these two energies, known as the energy gap (E_g), is an indicator of the molecule's chemical stability and electron conductivity [96]. In this study, we examined the complexes of Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb and found that the electron density of the HOMO was distributed on the heavy metal atoms, while the LUMO was localized on the phenyl and acetynyl groups. We calculated the E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} energies, as well as the energy gaps, for each of these complexes and found that the range of E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} values was between -3.474 and -7.401 eV. The Gp-NO₂-Pb complex had the most stable HOMO structure, while the Gp-NO₂-Cd complex had the least stable, as shown by comparing their respective E_{HOMO} values. However, comparison between the E_{LUMO} values shows that the Gp-NO₂-Cd complex has the most stable LUMO, while the Gp-NO₂-Pb complex has the least stable LUMO. Based on these findings, we conclude that the Gp-NO₂-Pb

complex is the most stable among the complexes studied, while the Gp-NO₂-Cd complex is the most reactive one. This is likely because Pb⁺² has the smallest ionic size among the heavy atoms under investigation. Fig. 5 provides a graphical representation of the HOMO and LUMO for each of these complexes.

Fig. 5 Graphical presentation of HOMO and LUMO of Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb.

3.7 Charge transfer analysis using NBO analysis.

Accurately determining the atomic charges of a molecular system is crucial for understanding its electrical characteristics [96]. The results of calculations using the M06-2X/LanL2DZ level of theory to determine the natural atomic charge, natural population, and natural electronic configuration of metal ions in Gp-NO₂ complexes are presented in Table 3. The Table 3 reveals that the computed charge on the metal ions is lower than the formal charge +2 because the oxygen in the nitrite group donates charge to the system. This indicates that electron density delocalization from the O-donor to the metal ion is high [96]. The electronic configuration for Cd, Hg, and Pb ions is [core]5s^(2.00)4d^(10.00)5p^(0.01), [core]6s^(1.98)5d^(10.00)6p^(0.01), and [core]6s^(1.94)6p^(1.64), respectively, according to Table 3. Therefore, Hg and Pb ions coordinate with the oxygen atoms of the nitrite group through their empty 6p orbitals, while the Cd ion coordinates through its empty 5p orbitals.

Table 3 Natural charge, population, and electronic configuration for Gp-NO₂ complexes using M06-2X/LanL2DZ level of theory.

Complexes	Natural charge	Natural population				Natural electronic configuration
		Core	Valence	Rydberg	Total	
Cd	-0.00293	36.00	12.00	0.00056	48.002	[core]5s ^(2.00) 4d ^(10.00) 5p ^(0.01)
Hg	0.00667	68.00	11.99	0.00145	79.993	[core]6s ^(1.98) 5d ^(10.00) 6p ^(0.01)
Pb	0.41103	78.00	3.583	0.00515	81.58897	[core]6s ^(1.94) 6p ^(1.64)

3.8 UV-Vis's spectra

In this study, the TD/M06-2X/LANL2DZ method was used to compute the electronic UV-Vis absorption spectra of Gp-NO₂ and its complexes (Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb). The results are presented in Fig. 6, and the relevant parameters are listed in Table 4.

Fig. 6 The calculated electronic absorption spectra for Gp-NO₂, Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb using TD/M06-2X/LANL2DZ.

The computed electronic absorption spectra for Gp-NO₂ and its complexes exhibit six transitions. Specifically, Gp-NO₂ shows electronic transitions at 467.02, 431.39, 431.38, 302.35, 300.35, and 347.25 nm, while Gp-NO₂-Cd exhibits transitions at 347.90, 369.34, 431.54, 431.78, 431.54, and 428.95 nm. Gp-NO₂-Hg shows transitions at 347.45, 356.31, 367.47, 371.35, 375.20, and 397.81 nm, and Gp-NO₂-Pb exhibits transitions at 328.59, 333.38, 339.67, 344.56, 350.89, and 357.73 nm. According to Fig. 6, the maximum absorption wavelengths for Gp-NO₂, Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb are 302, 347, 348, and 350 nm, respectively. These wavelengths correspond to electronic transitions from H→L, H-3→L, H-3→L, and H→L+2, respectively. The computational absorption spectra for Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-

NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb are red-shifted compared to that of Gp-NO₂, indicating how heavy metals (Cd⁺², Hg⁺², and Pb⁺²) coordinate with the NO₂ group in Gp-NO₂. It is clearly seen from Fig. 6 that intensity of the strongest absorption peak correlates with the type of the heavy metal ion, while its position is almost insensitive to the ion type.

Table 4. Calculated electronic absorption of Gp-NO₂, Gp-NO₂-Cd, Gp-NO₂-Hg, and Gp-NO₂-Pb using TD/M06-2X/LANL2DZ.

TD-Computational				
Gp-NO ₂				
Excited state	Electronic transitions	ΔE (eV)	f	Coefficient
1	H -> L	2.6548 (467.02nm)	0.000	0.44707
	H -> L+2			-0.12134
2	H -> L	2.8741(431.39nm)	0.3191	0.10612
	H -> L+1			-0.44080
3	H -> L	2.8741(431.38nm)	0.3191	0.44111
	H -> L+2			0.10662
	H-1 -> L+2			0.44104
4	H -> L+2	4.1280(302.35nm)	0.2467	0.12897
	H -> L			0.15309
	H -> L+6			-0.42729
5	H -> L+4	4.1280(300.35nm)	0.0001	0.43912
	H-1 -> L+5			0.43884
6	H -> L+7	3.5705(347.25 nm)	0.6337	0.10449
	H-1 -> L+6			-0.16822
Gp-NO ₂ -Cd				
1	H-2-> L+7	3.5638(347.90nm)	0.6212	-0.14085
	H-3 -> L			-0.54211
2	H -3-> L+2	3.3570(369.34 nm)	0.0010	0.35617
	H -5-> L+1			0.38953
3	H -1-> L+1	2.8730 (431.54 nm)	0.3026	0.36010
	H -2-> L+2			0.10902
	H-2 -> L+2			0.56691
4	H-1 -> L+1	2.8715(431.78nm)	0.3303	0.42660
	H-1-> L			0.20603
5	H -1-> L+1	2.8730(431.54nm)	0.3026	0.16869
	H -1-> L			0.50911
6	H -2-> L+1	2.8904(428.95nm)	0.0164	0.56691

H-1 -> L		0.36010		
Gp-NO ₂ -Hg				
1	H-1 -> L+6	3.5684(347.45nm)	0.6145	0.13603
	H-3-> L			0.54135
2	H-> L+7	3.4797(356.31nm)	0.0619	-0.37933
	H -> L+6			0.45421
3	H -> L+3	3.3740(367.47nm)	0.0012	0.22379
	H -> L+2			0.34342
4	H -> L+3	3.3387(371.35nm)	0.0010	0.26292
	H -> L+2			0.42561
5	H -> L+2	3.3045(375.20nm)	0.0030	0.25897
	H -> L			0.12678
6	H-> L	3.1167(397.81nm)	0.0075	0.39508
	H-> L+1			0.12785
Gp-NO ₂ -Pb				
1	H-1-> L+8	3.7732(328.59nm)	0.1534	0.17742
	H-1 -> L+6			0.23321
2	H -> L+7	3.7190(333.38nm)	0.0047	0.13344
	H -> L+5			0.43270
3	H -> L+4	3.6501(339.67nm)	0.0927	0.14683
	H -> L+3			0.12480
4	H -> L+7	3.5983(344.56nm)	0.1717	0.1572
	H -> L+5			0.10833
5	H -> L+2	3.5334(350.89nm)	0.2152	0.18465
	H -> L+3			0.38275
6	H -> L	3.4659(357.73nm)	0.0019	0.21486
	H -> L+3			0.21969

Conclusion

The density functional theory computations are used to examine the geometrical stability and electronic characteristics of chemically functionalized graphyne (Gp). Also considered is the complexation with heavy elements. We discovered that chemical functionalization makes Gp more reactive, which in turn enhances its capacity to bind to heavy metals. For instance, due to its high binding energy, Gp-NO₂ was chosen for complexation with the following heavy metal ions: Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺, and Cd²⁺. The absorption spectrum of Gp-NO₂ shifts to lower energies after forming complexes with all selected heavy metal ions. This red shift can be used as a characterization of the Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, and Pb²⁺ adsorption process. Notably, the

intensity of the major peak can be used to differentiate between the adsorbed ion types. The coordination connection between the NO₂ group and the heavy metals that interact with Gp-NO₂ was also confirmed using TD-DFT calculations. The oxygen in the nitrite group, which provides the charge to the heavy metals under study, is responsible for the calculated charge on the metal ions being lower than the formal charge +2. This conclusion was further supported by the NBO analysis. Thus, NO₂ functionalized γ -graphyne is a promising candidate for wastewater treatment. In addition, NO₂ functionalized γ -graphyne can be used as sensitive detector that allows a remote data read-out in a visible range of spectrum.

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Author contributions

Mahmoud A. S. Sakr: Writing-review and editing, Mohamed A. Saad: Software and calculations, Vasil A. Saroka: Data Curation, Visualization and Investigation, Hazem Abdelsalam Visualization, and Investigation, Qinfang Zhang: Visualization and Investigation.

Data availability All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

Declarations

Ethical Approval: This article does not contain any studies involving animals performed by any of the authors.

Consent to Participate: This article does not contain any studies involving animals performed by any of the authors.

Consent to Publish: All authors mentioned in the manuscript have given consent for submission and subsequent publication of the manuscript.

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